

PROGNOSTIC FACTORS AND INTERVENTIONS OF
MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT *ACINETOBACTER BAUMANNII*
INFECTION FOLLOWING LUNG CANCER RESECTION IN THE
ELDERLY

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Abstract

Objective: To investigate the contributing variables to multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (MDR- AB) infection following lung cancer resection among the elderly and to examined the nursing intervention. Methods: The study subjects were selected in January 2020 to January 2022 as 120 elderly postoperative MDR-AB infections after lung cancer resection and compared the clinical characteristics of the two groups (non-MDR-AB group and MDR-AB group) and the risk factors affecting the onset of MDR-AB were

analyzed based on multifactorial logistic regression. Results: Out of 120 patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* infections, 18 cases of drug sensitivity test pathogens were MDR-AB and 102 non-MDR-AB infections were found, respectively. Univariate analysis revealed that respiratory disease, age, comorbid diabetes mellitus, central venous catheterization. The exposure to carbapenem, cephalosporin, the use of more than 2 types of antimicrobials, the use of antimicrobials of more than 7 days and the APACHE II scores were higher in MDR-AB compared to the non-MDR-AB group

and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). The laboratory indicators, Hb and Alb were lower in the MDR-AB group compared with the non-MDR-AB group and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) and WBC, PCT and CRP were higher compared to the non-MDR-AB group and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). It was demonstrated in multifactorial logistic regression analysis that APACHE II score were above 16.97 g/L, combination of respiratory diseases, exposure to carbapenem, cephalosporin, exposure to antimicrobial drug more than 2 and more than 7 days, Hb less than 110.67 g/L, and Alb less than 33.34 g/L were the risk factors of MDR-AB infection. In conclusion, the risk factors that elevate the MDR-AB infection following lung cancer surgery in the elderly include basic diseases, invasive operations, use of antimicrobial drugs and poor nutritional status, to prevent the occurrence of MDR-AB, the positive intervention ought to be administered during the clinical nursing.

INTRODUCTION

Clinically, multidrug-resistant organisms (MDRO) refer to bacteria that are resistant to three or more commonly used antibiotics at the same time [1]. The emergence of MDROs has made the treatment of infectious diseases more difficult. How to prevent and control MDROs is the focus of attention of clinicians and infection managers. *Acinetobacter baumannii* is an opportunistic pathogen, and it becomes one of the main pathogens of acquired infections in the respiratory system, blood system, urinary system, etc. when the body's immunity is reduced. Studies have found that although the pathogenicity of multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (MDR-AB) is weak, it spreads quickly and is highly prevalent. For elderly patients or patients with surgical stress, it is still one of the more difficult pathogens in clinical practice. Therefore, this study investigated the occurrence of MDR-AB infection after lung cancer resection in elderly patients and analyzed the relevant influencing factors of MDR-AB infection.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Subjects

120 elderly patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection after lung cancer surgery from January 2020 to January 2022 were selected as the subjects, including 71 males and 49 females. The age ranged from 60 to 78 years, with an average of 68.22 ± 5.11 years. Inclusion criteria: age ≥ 60 years; infection diagnosis was based on the Hospital Infection Diagnosis Standard (Trial) of the Ministry of Health from Pakistan in 2001 [3]; multidrug resistance diagnosis was based on the Technical Guidelines for Prevention and Control of Hospital Infection of Multidrug-resistant Bacteria (Trial) [4]; the results of at least one bacterial culture showed *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and at the same time, it was resistant to at least three types of antibacterial drugs: penicillins, fluoroquinolones, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, and compound preparations containing β -lactamase inhibitors; complete clinical data. Exclusion criteria: age < 60 years; patients with infections or mixed infections caused by other pathogens; patients with metastasis of tumors in other parts; patients with incomplete clinical data. Informed consent was obtained from all patients or their families.

Survey Content

- (1) Basic information: including age, gender, body mass index (BMI), Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE II score), infection site (respiratory system, digestive system, urinary system, etc.), combined basic diseases (hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular system diseases, respiratory system diseases, nervous system diseases, digestive system diseases, etc.), invasive operations (central venous catheterization, indwelling gastric tube, indwelling urinary catheter, etc.), exposure to antibacterial drugs (carbapenem, cephalosporin, quinolone, aminoglycoside), combined use of antibacterial drugs and use time, etc.
- (2) Laboratory indicators: After all subjects were included in the study, venous blood was drawn in the morning on an empty stomach, and white blood cells (WBC) and hemoglobin (Hb) were detected by blood cell analysis instruments; albumin (Alb) levels were detected by a fully automatic biochemical analyzer; and procalcitonin levels (PCT) were detected by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA); C-

reactive protein levels (CRP) were detected by immunofluorescence dry quantitative method.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

SPSS23.0 statistical software was used to process the data. The measurement data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and the t-test was used to compare the mean between groups; the counting data were used to calculate the composition ratio, and the χ^2 test was used to compare the composition ratio between groups. Multivariate analysis was performed using a non-conditional logistic regression model, and the stepwise backward method was used for variable selection and elimination. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Analysis of MDR-AB Infection

Among 120 patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection, 18 cases of drug sensitivity test pathogens were MDR-AB, accounting for 15.00%; 102 cases were non-MDR-AB infection, accounting for 85.00%. The infection sites of both the MDR-AB group and the non-MDR-AB group were mainly respiratory tract infections, and the specific composition of the infection sites of the two groups is shown in **Table 1**.

Comparison of clinical characteristics between MDR-AB group and non-MDR-AB group

The age, proportion of patients with diabetes, respiratory diseases, central venous catheterization, carbapenem exposure, cephalosporin exposure, ≥ 2 types of antimicrobial drugs, ≥ 7 d of antimicrobial drugs and APACHE II score in MDR-AB group were higher than those in non-MDR-AB group, and the differences were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), as shown in **Table 2**.

Comparison of Laboratory Indicators between MDR-AB Group and Non-MDR-AB Group

The Hb and Alb of MDR-AB group were lower than those of non-MDR-AB group, while WBC, PCT and CRP were higher than those of non-MDR-AB group. The

differences between the groups were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), as shown in **Table 3**.

Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing MDR-AB Infection

Whether MDR-AB infection was taken as the dependent variable (yes = 1, no = 0), and APACHE II score (≥ 16.97 points = 1, < 16.97 points = 0), respiratory system disease (yes = 1, no = 0), hydrocarbon Enzyme alkene exposure (yes = 1, no = 0), cephalosporins (yes = 1, no = 0), types of antimicrobial drugs used (≥ 2 types = 1, < 2 types = 0), duration of antimicrobial drug use (≥ 7 d = 1, < 7 d = 0), Hb (≤ 110.67 g/L = 1, > 110.67 g/L = 0), and Alb (≤ 33.34 g/L = 1, > 33.34 g/L = 0) were used as independent variables for multivariate logistic regression analysis. The results showed that APACHE II score ≥ 16.97 , combined with respiratory system diseases, carbapenem exposure, cephalosporin exposure, ≥ 2 types of antimicrobial drugs used, ≥ 7 d of antimicrobial drugs used, Hb ≤ 110.67 g/L, and Alb ≤ 33.34 g/L were risk factors for MDR-AB infection ($P < 0.05$), as shown in **Table 3**.

Table 1. Proportion of infection sites in the MDR-AB and non-MDR-AB groups (%)

Infection site	MDR-AB Group (n=18)		Non-MDR-AB Group	
	Number of cases	Composition ratio (%)	Number of cases	Composition ratio (%)
digestive tract system infection	1	5.56	5	4.90
Respiratory tract infection	13	72.22	77	75.49
Urinary tract infection	1	5.56	2	1.96
Incision infection	1	5.56	6	5.88
Bloodstream infection	2	11.11	12	11.76

Table 2 Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of the Incidence of MDR-AB Infection

Variable	B	Se	Wald χ^2 Value	P Value	Or	Or 95%Ci
APACHE II score \geq 16.97	0.463	0.223	4.306	0.038	1.589	1.026 ~2.461
respiratory diseases	0.949	0.100	89.230	0.000	2.584	2.122 ~3.147
Hydrocarbon ene exposure	0.976	0.352	7.701	0.006	2.654	1.332 ~5.288
Cephalosporins \geq 2 types of antimicrobial drugs used	1.417	0.590	5.771	0.016	4.123	1.298 ~13.096
Antimicrobial use duration \geq 7 days	1.424	0.245	33.781	0.000	4.152	2.569 ~6.710
Hb \leq 110.67 g/L	1.135	0.115	139.667	0.000	3.885	3.102 ~4.866
Alb \leq 33.34 g/L	0.981	0.342	8.243	0.004	2.666	1.365 ~5.207
constant term	1.516	0.823	8.843	0.000	-	-

Table 3: Comparison of laboratory parameters between MDR-AB and non-MDR-AB group

Laboratory indicators	MDR-AB group (n=18)	Non-MDR-AB group (n=102)	t value	P value
WBC($\times 10^9$ /L)	16.15 \pm 1.68	12.21 \pm 1.42	10.553	0.000
Hb (g/L)	107.56 \pm 12.54	116.43 \pm 10.54	3.197	0.001

Alb (g/L)	32.14±2.45	36.43±2.75	6.195	0.000
PCT(ng/ml)	1.68±0.72	1.11±0.43	4.619	0.000
CRP(mg/L)	16.32±3.34	13.48±3.42	3.259	0.001

DISCUSSION

AB is the main pathogenic bacteria of hospital infection, widely distributed in the natural environment and hospital environment, and can be fixed in hospitalized patients. It is called "super bacteria", which has the characteristics of strong transmission, multiple and extensive drug resistance. MDR-AB is a gram-negative conditional pathogen, lacking effective drugs to fight against it, which leads to the increase of patients' hospitalization time, increases the difficulty of treatment, and brings great challenges to global anti-infection. MDR-AB can exist in the skin, respiratory tract and other parts of the human body, and has always been the main conditional pathogenic bacteria causing nosocomial infections [5]. *Acinetobacter baumannii* has strong resistance to wet heat, chemical disinfectants, ultraviolet rays, etc., and has strong survival ability. In recent years, the widespread and unreasonable use of broad-spectrum antibacterial drugs, especially carbapenem antibacterial drugs, has given the opportunity to screen out multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*, making the detection rate of MDRAB increase year by year [6]. Especially for the elderly, they generally have low immunity and are combined with a variety of diseases. It is inevitable to use antibacterial drugs for treatment, so they are more likely to be infected, which eventually leads to the occurrence of bacterial resistance. In this study, 18 of 120 patients with *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection had MDR-AB as the pathogen in the drug sensitivity test, accounting for 15.00%, and 102 patients had non-MDR-AB infection, accounting for 85.00%.

It can be seen that the incidence of MDR-AB infection in this type of patients is high. However, there was no significant difference in the type and site of infection caused by *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection between the two groups. Clinically, understanding the risk factors for infection in patients with a certain disease can provide necessary intervention in advance. Elderly patients with lung cancer already have

reduced body resistance, and the stress caused by surgical trauma further reduces the body's immune function. Therefore, controlling the risk factors that can be intervened as much as possible is of great clinical value for preventing the occurrence of MDR-AB. The analysis of this study found that age, diabetes, respiratory diseases, central venous catheterization, carbapenem exposure, cephalosporin exposure, quinolone exposure, types and duration of antimicrobial drugs, APACHE II score, Hb, Alb, WBC, PCT, and CRP levels were all related to the occurrence of MDR-AB infection. Further multivariate Logistic regression analysis found that APACHE II score ≥ 16.97 points, combined respiratory diseases, carbapenem exposure, cephalosporin exposure, ≥ 2 types of antimicrobial drugs, ≥ 7 days of antimicrobial drugs, Hb ≤ 110.67 g/L, and Alb ≤ 33.34 g/L were risk factors for MDR-AB infection after surgery for elderly patients with lung cancer. The results are consistent with previous studies. The analysis suggests that the original respiratory tract ciliary defense mechanism of elderly patients with respiratory diseases has been destroyed, so the respiratory tract defense function is seriously reduced, providing conditions for MDR-AB colonization [7-8]. Some studies have found that exposure to carbapenem and cephalosporin antibiotics can increase the incidence of carbapenem resistance, mainly because carbapenem and cephalosporin antibiotics can activate the porin protein penetration defects and the overexpression of efflux pumps of *Acinetobacter baumannii*, that is, activate other drug resistance mechanisms of *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Similarly, the combined use of antimicrobial drugs and prolonged use can increase the resistance of *Acinetobacter baumannii* [11-12]. For elderly patients with lung cancer, the consumption of nutrients by the growth of cancer cells may have caused different degrees of nutritional dysfunction in the body, which has affected the body's ability to defend against pathogens [13-15]. The lower the Alb and Hb, the worse the nutritional status of the body, the lower the ability to clear MDR-AB, and the higher the risk of infection [16-17]. Because the subjects included in this study were elderly patients with lung cancer after surgery, the indicators related to stress response after surgery, such as WBC and CRP, were further analyzed, but the results did not find that they could be used as risk factors for MDR-AB infection. The analysis suggests that WBC and CRP are the most commonly used reference indicators

for infection and stress response in clinical practice, and have high sensitivity. However, since MDR-AB is similar to ordinary *Acinetobacter baumannii* in morphology, biological characteristics, and requirements for the living environment [18-20], it does not increase the risk of MDR-AB.

In clinical settings, it is necessary to actively strengthen the management of the respiratory tract, and on the basis of giving patients continuous low-flow oxygen inhalation, guide patients to cough and expectorate better, and give patients regular turning over and back patting to further promote sputum discharge. In the daily nursing process, it is necessary to open the window for ventilation frequently to avoid cross-infection of patients. Raise the head of the bed according to the patient's condition. Strictly implement the seven-step hand washing method to wash hands, spray hands with hand disinfectant before replacing the infusion joint, then disinfect the infusion joint with an iodine solution, wear masks and hats during the nursing process, and disinfect the skin of the puncture point with chlorhexidine solution.

In summary, this study shows that the incidence of MDRAB infection after surgery for elderly patients with lung cancer is high, and basic diseases, invasive operations, antibiotic use, and poor nutritional status can increase the risk of its occurrence.

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